

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE VARIATION IN MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATES IMMERSSED IN WATER BY A NON DESTRUCTIVE METHOD

Ph. CASTAING (1), L. LEMOINE (2), N. TSOVALIS (3)

(1) CETIM, Dept. of Polymers & Composite Materials, BP 957, 44076 NANTES (FRANCE)

(2) IFREMER, Marine Materials Laboratory, BP 70, 29280 PLOUZANE (FRANCE)

(3) NTUA., Dept. of Naval Architecture & Marine Eng., BP 64070, 15710 ZOGRAFOS (GREECE)

ABSTRACT

Glass Fibre Reinforced Polyester Composites, with gelcoat, are widely used as structural materials for hulls, pools... in aggressive environments, despite their relatively weak resistance to water at long term. In addition, these materials may be damaged through an osmotic process, especially when immersed in water like boat hulls are, and that phenomenon can lead to a delamination of the gelcoat and of the laminate plies. Thus, predicting the life time of these materials is of great interest. The aim of the experimental study presented in this paper is to evaluate the mechanical characteristics with time of orthotropic laminates subjected to accelerated tests of ageing. The properties are followed by a non destructive test procedure based on vibrational modal analysis, and the results are additionally confirmed by quasi-static bending and shear tests. It is shown that the main effects of water on the composite mechanical properties are the plasticization of the matrix and the osmotic delamination of the plies; on the other hand, gelcoat blistering has no influence on the durability. This paper highlights the need for and the complementarity of both non destructive and destructive mechanical tests for studying the long term behaviour of composites in marine environments.

KEY WORDS : composites, polyester, glass fibre, gelcoat, ageing, osmosis, delamination, durability, mechanical properties, modal analysis, shear, bending

1- INTRODUCTION

Glass fibre reinforced polyester composites are widely used in nautical construction mainly due to their improved properties compared to traditional structural materials. Composite materials offer a good long term behaviour and high strength - stiffness- to weight ratios, and a good long term behaviour in various aggressive environments. In fact, it appears that reinforced polyester materials are particularly sensitive to humidity through an absorption of water, leading to physical degradations, like the plasticization of the matrix with water and the differential swelling between the fibres and the resin. The uptake of water can also lead to chemical degradations like hydrolysis of the matrix and of the glass sizing.

In addition to these degradations, an osmotic process can lead to a delamination of the gelcoat under circular blisters and the laminate plies under ellipsoidal shaped defects (1, 2). The problem may affect 20 to 30 % of reinforced polyester hulls and also composite swimming-pools, after twenty years of immersion in sea water (3).

All the phenomena governing the fluxes of aqueous solutions through semi-permeable membranes, and particularly through cellular membranes of living organisms, are described under the term "Osmosis". The process takes place when a solvent and an aqueous solution are separated by a semi-

permeable membrane, that is to say permeable only to the solvent. A flux of solvent resulting from the solutes concentration gradient, arises through the wall to re-equilibrate the concentration and a hydrostatic pressure (osmotic) is generated, opposing to that flux. It is now well known that unsaturated polyester, epoxy resins and also laminate plies behave like osmotic membranes. (4, 5).

The osmotic delamination may only be cosmetic (gelcoat blistering) or more serious causing a loss of properties. Thus predicting the life time of materials in sea or fresh water is of great interest.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the retention of mechanical properties of gelcoated orthotropic laminates, induced by accelerated tests of blistering and ageing in distilled water. The mechanical properties followed are the in plane moduli and the ultimate stresses, both in the direction of the fibres and in the transverse direction. This experimental procedure is mainly conducted using a non destructive method, the vibrational modal analysis, because of the difficulty to control periodically the mechanical properties of a large number of samples during an ageing study. In addition, non destructive methods offer an increasing interest in studying the long term behaviour of composites in extreme environments because of the possibility to evaluate accurately and continuously the durability of a structure in service.

Nonetheless, in this study the properties are confirmed by complementary static bending tests (3 point bending and interlaminar shear).

Finally, the work described in this paper enables us to forecast more accurately the life time of polyester structures like hulls subjected to temperature and humid environment.

2- MATERIALS AND AGEING

2-1 MATERIALS TESTED

The composites used are E-glass reinforced unsaturated polyesters, whose laminate resins, which are commonly used in nautical construction, are orthophthalic (referred to as ORTHO laminate), isophthalic filled with microspheres (4 to 5 % in weight) of SiO_2 (ISO with thixotropic fillers or ISOTHIXO laminate) or not filled (ISO laminate) (CRAY VALLEY FRANCE). The laminates are coated with a gelcoat, which is a white coloured isoneopentylglycol (ISONPG) polyester resin, filled with TiO_2 and supplied by FERRO FRANCE. The laminates are reinforced with ten layers of quasi-unidirectional woven fibres (88%-12%, 290 g/m^2), the volume fibre ratio obtained is 40%. The manufacturing process is similar to that used in polyester shipbuilding and consists of gun-spraying the gelcoat in order to get a mean thickness of 0.3 mm, and hand laying-up the laminate. The curing is performed at room temperature (20°C for this study) for two months.

2-2 AGEING PROCEDURE

Samples (400 mm x 300 mm x 3 mm) are immersed in distilled water at a temperature of $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ for 5000 hours. A previous study (2, 6) confirmed the osmotic origin of the delamination by blistering and showed that a sufficient accelerating factor is obtained at that temperature, compared to a natural ageing test in sea water.

The osmotic delamination takes place in two steps :

-from 200 to 3000 hours of immersion, circular blisters appear on the gelcoat; then a steady state is reached so that the osmotic process is stopped;

-from 3000 hours to 5000 hours, ellipsoidal shaped defects grow between the two first plies, and then the process is stopped; the larger radius of the defect is parallel to the fibres. The ratio of large radius to small radius of the elliptic defect is found to be proportional to the longitudinal to transverse modulus ratio (2, 6).

-for times above 5000 hours, a delamination is initiated between the second and the third ply.

It can be deduced from these observations that the osmotic delamination of the plies may be more serious than the gelcoat blistering.

3- MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

3-1 PROPERTIES MEASURED

The gelcoated laminates studied are considered to be orthotropic and so they are defined under plane stress by four independant elastic constants :

E_1 is the elastic modulus parallel to the fibres or longitudinal modulus;

E_2 is the modulus in the direction perpendicular to the reinforcement (transverse modulus);
 G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus;
 ν_{12} is the longitudinal Poisson's ratio.

The ultimate stresses determined in this study are as follows :

σ_{r1} is the ultimate flexural stress in the longitudinal direction;
 σ_{r2} is the ultimate flexural stress in the transverse direction;
 τ_{r1} is the ultimate interlaminar shear stress in the longitudinal direction;

It remains essential to determine the mechanical characteristics in the transverse direction (because they describe the degradation of the matrix) and the shear properties, as they show the degradation of the bond between matrix and fibres.

The destructive mechanical tests are 3 point bending (standard EN 63) and interlaminar shear tests (standard NFT 57107, or ISO 4585). These tests need a large amount of beam or dog-bone shaped samples when the ageing time is long. In addition, it is difficult to quantify the influence of water absorption through the lateral faces of beams. Thus E_1 , E_2 , σ_{r1} , σ_{r2} , τ_{r1} and τ_{r2} are measured only at initial state, after 2000 hours of immersion when the gelcoat blistering has appeared, and then after 5000 hours of immersion when the delamination of the first ply has occurred.

A closer determination of the in-plane moduli E_1 , E_2 and G_{12} , (every 200 hours of immersion) is carried out by modal analysis experiments on plates. The two methods are complementary to characterize the whole plate under plane stress.

3-2 MODAL ANALYSIS

The method has been developed (7, 8) to evaluate the mechanical properties of rectangular, anisotropic and homogeneous plates with four free edges. It consists of two steps : in the first one, the natural frequencies of the plate are measured using accelerometers and their associated modeshapes are identified.

The plate is excited with a small hammer to stress the laminate under a bending moment. Then the approximate rigidities of the plate are introduced in a theoretical model so that the calculated natural frequencies match as closely as possible the corresponding experimental values.

The theoretical model of the vibrational behaviour of an anisotropic plate is based on the classical Theory of Plates (9, 10) under plane stress. The plate rigidities identification is done by means of an iterative method (7), where possible measurement errors or rigidities uncertainties are provided from another simple and quick theoretical model, with the aid of the min-max approximation optimization method. The validity of both the model for the calculation of the resonance frequencies and the modeshapes as well as of the rigidities optimization method were verified through several numerical studies, while the influence of the mass of the accelerometers used in the experiment was also investigated.

The frequencies in Hz of orthotropic rectangular free edges plates are as follows :

$$f_{i,j}^2 = \frac{\pi^2}{4\rho h} \left[\frac{G_1^4 \cdot D_{11}}{a^4} + \frac{G_2^4 \cdot D_{22}}{b^4} + \frac{2 \cdot H_1 \cdot H_2 \cdot D_k}{a^2 b^2} + \frac{D_{66} \cdot (J_1 J_2 - H_1 H_2)}{a^2 b^2} \right]$$

where f_{ij} is the natural frequency in Hz; i, j are the number of nodes in x and y directions respectively, ρ is the density, h the thickness, a the length (in x direction), b the width (in y direction) of the plate respectively and G_n , H_n , J_n , are constant functions of the indices i, j (7, 8, 9, 10).

The rigidities are defined as follows :

$$D_{11} = \frac{E_1 \cdot h^3}{12(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})} ; D_{12} = \frac{E_2 \cdot h^3}{12(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})} ; D_k = D_{12} + 2 \cdot D_{66} ; D_{12} = \nu_{21} D_{11} ; D_{66} = \frac{1}{12} G_{12} \cdot h^3$$

The rigidities are deduced from the frequencies f_{ij} ; knowing the first five natural frequencies and their associated modeshapes, allows us to determinate the elastic constants E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , ν_{12} . In the framework of this study, only the in-plane moduli are followed.

An example of the natural frequencies of the 3 laminates studied is given in Table 1. The associated modeshapes for square plates are represented on Figure 1.

This method also allows the study of the damping of the materials and thus the viscoelastic behaviour, and its evolution with time of ageing, but that is not treated in the current paper.

4- VARIATION OF THE PROPERTIES WITH TIME

4-1 EVOLUTION OF THE IN-PLANE MODULI

The variations of the in plane moduli $E_1=f(t)$, $E_2=g(t)$, $G_{12}=h(t)$ determined by modal analysis are quite similar for the laminates ORTHO, ISO and ISOTHIXO as shown on Figure 2. A first decrease is observed from 300 hours to 600 hours (5% for ISO & ISOTHIXO, 10% for ORTHO), followed by a linear loss of properties up to 2000-3000 hours. The properties degradation continues to be smooth up to 5000 hours, resulting in a final large decrease with respect to the initial state. The decline of the moduli is more important in the transverse direction compared to the longitudinal direction as expected : the matrix and the glass sizing are preferentially attacked by water in the perpendicular direction, while the longitudinal fibres seems to keep their integrity. The decrease is especially high for ORTHO laminates, whose matrix is more sensitive to water than the ISO resins.

The first decrease of the moduli is mainly assigned to the plasticization of the laminate matrix with water molecules, even if gelcoat blistering initiates in this period : while blisters are growing, for times longer than 500 hours till 3000 hours, the loss remains low.

The gelcoat blistering seems to have no effect on the structure integrity. For times beyond 2500-3000 hours, corresponding to the osmotic delamination of the first ply, another decrease of the moduli appears mainly in the transverse direction (E_2) but also in the fibre direction especially for the ORTHO laminates, The shear modulus G_{12} , which particularly characterizes the intralaminar bond, also decreases for all the materials, and the fall is more important for ORTHO laminates (Figure 3).

For comparison, Table 2 reports the values of E_1 and E_2 measured by 3 point bending tests in the initial state, after 2000 hours and after 5000 hours of immersion. These values are also reported on Figure 2, and a good agreement of the results is obtained with the two methods.

4-2 EVOLUTION OF THE ULTIMATE STRESSES

The ultimate stresses measured at $t=0$ hour, $t=2000$ hours and $t=5000$ hours are the flexural ultimate stresses and the interlaminar shear stresses, both in the longitudinal and in the transverse directions. The interlaminar shear stresses characterize the interface matrix-fibres and its degradation. The results, reported in Table 3, show that ISO laminates are less severely damaged than the ORTHO ones : the relative decrease for the ISO is about 10% to 20% of the initial properties after 2000 hours and 25-30% after 5000 hours of immersion; on the contrary, the relative loss is about 20-30% for the ORTHO after 2000 hours and 40 to 65% after 5000 hours. The relative loss of properties is higher in the transverse direction, and in the shear behaviour : not only the matrix, but the bond between the resin and the fibres are severely attacked by hydrolysis. For ORTHO materials, the relative loss might be 100% in some areas when a delamination has propagated. A superior behaviour of the ISO is then observed as its residual properties remains twice those for the ORTHO: the ISO durability can be considered to be twice as long; also, the relative residual properties can be considered good as they are about 70% of the initial state after 5000 hours and about 80% of the properties could be recovered since the plasticization of the resin with water is reversible after drying (11). However, some authors (12) believe that the phenomenon of plasticization is chemically reversible but produces permanent effects on the mechanical behaviour of a composite, so this information must be taken into account to predict the durability.

Concerning the behaviour of the ISOTHIXO laminates, their residual properties are lower than for the ISO but remain much better than for the ORTHO. This is due to the microspheres of SiO_2 , which create a certain number of interfaces filler-organic resin mineral, more sensitive to an hydrolytic attack.

5- CONCLUSION

The proposed experimental procedure is adequate for an estimate of loss of mechanical properties of GFRP subjected to humid ageing in marine environment.

The decrease of mechanical characteristics is very significant for the ORTHO materials, a fact owing to the hydrolytic attack to which this resin is more sensitive than ISO resins, mainly for chemical reasons (average molecular number lower, orthophthalic acid more hydrosoluble, insaturation ratio and copolymerization with styrene rate lower). On the other hand, the residual properties of the ISO materials remain reasonable without affecting the integrity of the structure, even under an osmotic attack : the life time of the ISOs is twice as long as for the ORTHOs. This study also shows that the effect of plasticization (of the laminate resin) and of the osmotic delamination of the plies are more important than the gelcoat blistering which affects only the "skin" of the structures and which remains only a cosmetic problem. As the delamination of the plies may happen after 20 or 30 years of immersion at room temperature, the plasticization of the material with water remains the main consequence of absorption.

The modal analysis method used to evaluate the mechanical properties of rectangular anisotropic plates constitutes a very useful tool, requiring little instrumentation, allowing us to estimate with a great accuracy four elastic constants at the same time and with only one experiment. Although complementary destructive tests are necessary to get information concerning the ultimate stresses, the method permits us to determine the in plane shear modulus, and can be applied to large structures in service. Another interest of the modal analysis is that it can be used to control continuously the same structure during long times and furthermore, to measure the damping of the material and estimate its viscoelastic behaviour.

6- BIBLIOGRAPHY

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BIOGRAPHIES

Philippe CASTAING, engineer, Ph.D. graduate "Composite Materials", is in charge of the "PhysicoChemistry-Ageing of Composites" Laboratory, Dept. of Polymers & Composites, at CETIM (Technical Centre of Mechanical Industries).

Lionel LEMOINE, graduate engineer from INSA of Lyon, is in charge of the "Marine Materials" Laboratory, Department of Ocean Engineering at IFREMER (French Research Institute for Ocean Exploitation)

Nicholas TSOUVALIS, engineer, Ph.D. graduate 'Compoiste Structural Response', National Technical University of Athens.

Figure 1 : 3-D representation of the first five modeshapes of a laminate.

Figure 2 : Evolution of E_1 , longitudinal modulus, with time t for various laminates immersed in distilled water at $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ (modal analysis). (1) : ISO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (2) : ISOTHIXO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (3) : ORTHO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat.

Figure 3 : Evolution of E_2 , transverse modulus, with time t for various laminates immersed in distilled water at $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ (modal analysis). (1) : ISO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (2) : ISOTHIXO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (3) : ORTHO laminate with ISO NPG laminate.

Figure 4 : Evolution of G_{12} , in plane shear modulus, with time t for various laminates immersed in distilled water at $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ (modal analysis). (1) : ISO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (2) : ISOTHIXO laminate with ISONPG gelcoat; (3) : ORTHO laminate with ISO NPG laminate.

MODESHAPE	f (Hz) ISO	f(Hz) ISOTHIXO	f(Hz) ORTHO
mode 1,1	66,9	102,7	72,2
mode 2,0 (saddle)	126,3	116,9	134,6
mode 0,2 (breathing)	143,8	139,5	152,8
mode 2,1	187,5	155,1	198,7
mode 1,2	193,8		208,1

Table 1 : Experimental natural frequencies of the laminates studied at initial state.

MATERIAL	E ₁ (GPa)	E ₂ (GPa)
ORTHO initial	25.2	9.3
2000 hours	22.9 (-09.2%)	7.7 (-17.8%)
5000 hours	20.4 (-18.8%)	4.6 (-50.2%)
ISO initial	23.7	11.2
2000 hours		10.5 (-05.9%)
5000 hours	22.7 (-04.2%)	7.8 (-30.0%)
ISOTHIXO initial	20.5	10
2000 hours		8.4 (-16.1%)
5000 hours	18.4 (-10.2%)	5.5 (-44.3%)

Table 2 : Relative variations of the longitudinal and transversal moduli E₁, E₂, in GPa, after 2000 hours and 5000 hours of immersion in distilled water (60°C) for the laminates studied (3 point bending tests).

MATERIAL	σ_{r1} (MPa)	σ_{r2} (MPa)	τ_{r1} (Mpa)	τ_{r2} (Mpa)
ORTHO initial	509	102	67.8	18.1
2000 hours	430	81	44.5	11.7
5000 hours	286	50	19.9	07.7
ISO initial	578	112	66.2	16.1
2000 hours	535	108	53.1	13.1
5000 hours	475	100	47.2	12.3
ISOTHIXO initial	485	98	55.5	14.7
2000 hours	412	82	42.2	12.1
5000 hours	331	50	30.0	10.1

Table 3 : Variations of the ultimate stresses (bending and shear) in longitudinal and transversal directions σ_{r1} , σ_{r2} , τ_{r1} and τ_{r2} in MPa, after 2000 hours and 5000 hours of immersion in distilled water for the laminates studied (3 point bending and interlaminar shear).